

TERRITORIAL ADMINISTRATIVE UNIT - AUTONOMOUS ADMINISTRATIVE STRUCTURE

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Abstract: *The territorial administrative units are complex entities, with diversified organizational structures, within which a set of activities is developed for the elaboration and application of normative acts, methodological norms, regulations and programs, in order to meet the needs, needs and requirements of the local community within which act. The territorial administrative units have legal personality and comprise in their structure deliberative and executive authorities. Their main feature is that they work according to the principle of decentralization, which implies autonomy and the limited transfer of decision-making power from central to local level. Local autonomy gives territorial administrative units the right, within the limits set, to have initiatives in all areas concerning the respective local community. The territorial administrative units have their own budgets and have their own patrimony in which the goods belonging to the public and private domain of the county, the municipality, the city or the commune are included. They organize, operate and manage the financial resources and public or private property assets of communes, cities and municipalities, based on the principles of local autonomy, decentralization of public services, eligibility, legality and consultation of citizens in solving local problems of community interest.*

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Characteristics of territorial administrative units

The territorial administrative units comprise the communes, the cities, the municipalities, the sectors of the Bucharest municipality, the counties, the Bucharest municipality. In the subordination or coordination of the local public entities are the public services of local interest, organized at the level of economic operator, which have the role of realizing and providing public services, which satisfy the interests and needs of the citizens, who compose the local community in which the administrative unit territorial activity (Matei, & Anghelescu, 2009).

The characteristics of the territorial administrative units can be identified as follows:

a) *responsibility towards the citizen* - the territorial administrative units implement the policy of the government in the specific fields of activity, by virtue of the principles of autonomy and local decentralization, being the guarantor of the state at local level and have direct responsibility towards the citizen. Through the provision of public services, I aim to satisfy the needs and needs of the local community in which the public entity operates.

b) *rigidity in setting objectives* - the role of territorial administrative units is established by normative acts and is related to meeting the needs and needs of the local community in which it acts. In this situation, the territorial administrative units have the obligation to act within the established normative framework. They cannot restrict their activities, in cases where they are not efficient or realized under performance conditions, but they cannot extend them outside the limit established by the normative framework or they can be re-profiled.

c) *management based on objectives* - involves defining the strategic objectives, within the strategies and policies of the entity and deriving them into general objectives and then into specific objectives. This management system ensures the superior use of resources and obtaining performance, but for this must be harmonized: the set of objectives, regardless of the level at which they are defined and the hierarchical level; action programs, which include concrete ways to achieve the objectives; budgets, which approve the resources needed to achieve the objectives; the deadlines for implementing the actions; the methods, techniques and tools used to achieve the objectives. Goal-based management also emphasizes risk assessment and their impact on goal achievement, which is why internal control systems designed and implemented must lead to risk mitigation.

d) *the conditions of competition for conducting the activity* - the territorial administrative unit is a provider of public services to the citizens, but the activities carried out for their accomplishment do not subsume the concept of financial profitability, respectively, at present there are no established effective tools for evaluating their own activity and performance measurement. This has repercussions on the efficient use of public funds and ensuring transparency and maintains certain levels of bureaucracy.

e) *the election of the deliberative and executive authorities by vote* - mayors, presidents of county councils, members of local and county councils are appointed following the vote of citizens who are part of the local community where the public entity acts. Under these conditions, there is a close relationship between the public administration and the political environment, with positive or negative consequences.

f) *the authority of the leaders* - the leaders of the local public entities come into contact or work with persons from central authorities and public institutions, with leaders of interest groups, committees, commissions, etc., which can significantly affect their authority.

g) *human resources management* - current regulations in the field of human resources limit the possibilities of the managers of the territorial administrative units to hire, release from positions, sanction or reward.

The dimensioning of the structure of a territorial administrative unit is limited, this is done according to the number of citizens that exist in the area of action of the entity, without taking into account the conditions of technology and the concrete ways of carrying out the activities.

Dismissal or sanction of an employee is subject to the decision of a disciplinary committee. This methodology on the one hand is beneficial because it eliminates the direct possibility of the manager to sanction, in certain cases, persons with whom they conflict or who have opinions on certain decisions, but, on the other hand, the leader of the entity is responsible for achieving the objectives under performance conditions, which is why it has to have, directly, certain levers and tools for achieving the objectives. Also, existing career plans do not motivate employees to use professional skills in the interest of the entity and to make a career in that entity.

h) *measuring the organizational performance* - it involves taking into account the requirements regarding: if it was worked correctly and if it was done the right thing. The first requirement involves compliance with the regulations and requirements of the adopted strategy and operates in accordance with the “good practice” in the field. The second requirement relates to the effectiveness

of the programs, the activities carried out or the responsible functions and the achievement of the established results.

i) *correction against the citizen* - the territorial administrative unit is organized in such a way as to serve the interests of the citizens, but at the same time, it exercises its power and capacity to sanction on the citizen.

These characteristics impose a specific profile for the territorial administrative units and highlight that the efficient and effective functioning represents a managerial responsibility.

The existence of the limitations and structural problems that the territorial administrative units face, is influenced by the organizational culture and determines their leaders to find solutions to the existing problems so that the institutional performance increases.

At the organizational level, the organizational culture is influenced by a number of factors such as leadership style, decision making, organizational form, policies and strategies developed and applied, level of formalism or working environment. Also, the organizational culture is influenced by the aspirations and values system of the organization, by the knowledge and skills of the staff, by the interaction between the employees of the organization, by the goals and interests of the management and the employees. The management of the organization uses the organizational culture in making managerial decisions (Vasile & Croitoru, 2016).

Delimitations regarding the operating environment of the territorial administrative units

From the analysis of the way of organization and functioning of the territorial administrative units it has resulted that, at present, the best tools for the efficiency of activities are not applied, in areas such as the decision-making process, the establishment of responsibilities and functional relations, the decentralization of the activities, the independence of the budgets, the communication between the public entity and the citizen, as well as the implementation of an integrated information system.

In the current conditions of development of the company, we express our conviction that the complex political, social and economic environment, the structural and organizational changes that took place within the public entities, in the last period of time, have generated a professionalization process of the management in the public entities. The process must continue to involve the selection and attracting of specialized personnel, who have the necessary

competences to perform the functions and tasks of the entity and is able to apply modern management methods, techniques and approaches, in order to obtain performance.

In order to obtain performance, it is necessary to establish an adequate organizational structure, to analyze and correctly define the work processes, tasks, tasks, competences and responsibilities of the personnel, as well as to establish clear functional and representation relationships, both inside and outside. entity.

Under the current requirements, the performance of a public entity is determined according to the way in which human, material, informational and financial resources are used to achieve the objectives proposed at the level of performance standards and how they satisfy the public interest, through the services offered. Under these conditions, management's concern is how to manage public resources more efficiently to meet the social needs of citizens who are constantly growing and how to achieve the best level of performance, by ensuring the efficient functioning of the system from which the public institution makes part (Croitoru and Calotă, 2011).

The specific responsibilities established to the territorial administrative units according to the regulations in force and which influence the establishment and achievement of the objectives are:

a) *submission to the rule of law* - the organization and functioning of the entity, the carrying out of activities and actions, as well as the exercise of any function, attribution or task are only made if there is a regulatory framework in force. The methodological and procedural framework under which the activities are carried out is elaborated on the basis of the normative framework, any deviation from these rules leads to attracting the responsibility of the persons concerned.

b) *centralization of power and responsibility* - the power within a territorial administrative entity is concentrated at the top of the entity, where it is decided on the strategy and future development, in compliance with the legislative requirements in force.

The responsibility for achieving the objectives rests with the management, even if it delegates the execution of the activities of the lower levels. Also, the management is responsible for designing and elaborating the internal control system at the level of the whole entity, and the lower levels have the obligation to implement this system in the form decided by the management. Any imperfections are reported, and the top management decides on the systems review.

c) *the use of the career system in the recruitment of the personnel* - the career system is a rigid one, it does not ensure the co-interest and stability of the personnel on a certain function, there is no system of motivating the personnel, which limits the co-interest in accomplishing the tasks and the use of all professional skills. Also, after a certain period of work, the staff reaches the top of the career system without having a further motivation system.

d) *compliance with procedures and initiative* - the management issues decisions that are applied in the form received by all the hierarchical levels and all the managers. The limitation of the initiative creates a certain rigidity in the accomplishment of the activities, because the lack of the possibility to make decisions, within the limits of the established responsibilities, does not ensure efficiency in the accomplishment of the tasks and reduces the level of performance.

e) *the diversification of the role of the territorial administrative units* - the needs and needs of the citizens are constantly increasing and diversifying, which require the entity to expand and diversify its activities so as to find solutions to meet these needs. The process is complex, involves the deliberative authority that is responsible for the adoption of the decisions and the executive authority that is responsible for identifying the resources necessary for the realization of the public services requested by the citizens and the implementation of the decisions taken.

f) *budgetary pressure* - budgeting through programs has not yet become a basic tool for the management of territorial administrative units, although the measurement of the degree of achievement of objectives, with the help of defined indicators, is also done in financial terms. Program budgeting plays an important role in ensuring performance. The object of the budget of the program is to establish as rigorously as possible the volume of incomes, their structure by sources and expenditures by destinations.

g) *the technologicalization of the territorial administrative units* - the development of information technology is an essential condition in ensuring the performance and reducing the costs, it allows the reduction of the physical work, the information storage and the achievement of efficient information circuits. The provision of integrated information circuits makes it possible to have complete and updated databases, which can provide information for any field of activity of the entity.

h) *application of good practices* - application of international standards in the field and of good practice is a current responsibility and activity. This facilitates the possibility of applying unitary methodologies for carrying out

the activities, preparing reports and providing clear information about the entity and its economic situation.

In these conditions of organization and functioning, the implementation of the performance concept within the territorial administrative units represents a difficult thing to do, considering the difficulties regarding the understanding of the performance concept, the ways in which the performance can be ensured and) the difficulties regarding the establishment. performance measurement criteria, based on performance indicators (Săvulescu, Matei, Angheliescu, 2009).

However, changing the role of the administration in correlation with the needs of the citizens will lead to the need to make changes within the territorial administrative units, based on efficiency, efficiency, responsibility, decentralization, transparency, strategic approaches and quality.

Factors influencing the activity of territorial administrative units

The territorial administrative units have established general and specific functions and attributions and on their basis they perform and provide public services, in accordance with the general public need. Public services are financed from public funds and they benefit the entire community in the area where the territorial administrative unit operates.

At the same time, the rules established between the territorial administrative unit and the citizen ensure the identification of the general collective needs and the choice of the most appropriate public services to be provided, however, without the territorial administrative unit taking into account their own interests.

The balancing of collective interests and the provision of public services must take into account the needs of the community, identified by interests, values, concerns or behaviors (Popescu, 2015).

Thus, the greater the collective choices made by the territorial administrative unit in the provision of the public service, the more support the community enjoys, the more they accumulate an increased authority.

The main criteria considered when choosing and providing public services and which may represent values of the public administration sector are the following:

- a) clear identification of the needs and needs of the community;
- b) establishing a correct relationship with the citizen;
- c) responsibility towards the citizen and in carrying out public actions;
- d) equal treatment for each citizen, regardless of their status;

- e) involvement of the citizen in the decision making by the public entity;
- f) appreciation and respect by the territorial administrative unit of its employees, which represents the link between the entity and the citizen.

In our opinion, we consider that, within this system, the human resource is an important, decisive factor, which contributes to the provision of quality public services and in terms of efficiency and effectiveness. Under these conditions, increasing the professionalism and skills of the staff should be a fundamental requirement for the entity.

In the economic thinking and practice of territorial administrative units, several factors that influence the environment in which they operate are distinguished, as follows:

Technological conditions, a territorial administrative unit that has integrated information systems and technologies works better and ensures the transparency of activities.

Legal conditions, the territorial administrative unit defines its objectives and structures the activity according to the existing legal regulations, which means that, an appropriate regulatory framework is of utmost importance for the public entity;

Political conditions, the political environment has an obvious influence on the territorial administrative units, due to the fact that they are led by politicians who are the people's representatives, elected in public functions, by vote. However, politics can also have a negative influence on territorial administrative units, by "politicizing" after each electoral process, on criteria of political belonging and not through competence.

Demographic conditions, the structure and characteristics of the community of which the territorial administrative unit is part, have an important impact on the way of organization and functioning of the public administration, as well as the way of structuring;

Economic conditions, the activity of the territorial administrative units is influenced by the degree of economic development of the company, respectively by the level and the way of collecting the revenues and by the way of spending the public funds, which can make it or not competitive;

Cultural conditions are identified by the perception of the administration by the citizen and his confidence in the authorities.

Considering the variety, volume and complexity of the activities carried out within the territorial administrative unit, we can appreciate that it is difficult to understand and analyze if the environment in which it works is not known (Profiroiu, 2010).

Through its operating mechanisms, the territorial administrative unit has the possibility, by virtue of access to specialized information, to influence the conception of public policies and strategies and thus to develop its own institutional interest.

Strategic planning - a factor of progress in territorial administrative units

The territorial administrative unit faces increasingly complex problems, determined by the limitation of public resources and increasing expectations from citizens and the local community, which requires efforts to develop programs and to attract funds in order to achieve and provide the requested public services (Jaliu, 2013). The territorial administrative units tried to establish medium-term development visions, based on which they proceeded to design and elaborate more or less complex development strategies, depending on the objectives pursued. In this strategic development approach, the territorial administrative unit was confronted with a number of problems, as follows:

a) the flexibility and the accomplishment of the strategic changes at the level of the territorial administrative units are limited, being determined by the mission and the purpose of their organization and functioning which are established by legal regulations and from which they cannot be deviated;

b) the time periods established in the strategy for achieving and achieving the objectives are short, being determined by the limitation of the mandate of the leader, who is elected by vote by the citizens of the community and who wants immediate and visible results;

c) the process of establishing and defining the objectives is a complex one, influenced by the political, administrative, interest groups, as well as by the citizen;

d) the lack of professional training programs of the personnel involved in the implementation of the strategy leads to a limited diagnosis of the field, and in conjunction with the insufficiency of the information leads to the incorrect formulation of the strategy;

e) the complexity and variety of activities, as well as the goals pursued by the territorial administrative units make it difficult to measure the results obtained, especially the impact of achieving the strategic objectives on the entity.

Although, there is a risk management at the level of territorial administrative units, risk taking is not a type of behavior encouraged by the management of public entities, in the sense that the managerial responsibility regarding the internal control system is assumed, but the implementation and application, in practice, of these systems is insignificant.

Conclusions

In the last period of time, the specialists have shown, following the researches carried out that the main objective of the management of the territorial administrative units must be reviewed and oriented towards a system of values, respectively towards the evaluation of the performance. To achieve this objective, the directions of action are: how to manage public resources more efficiently, to meet the needs of the citizens constantly growing and how to obtain the best level of performance, by ensuring the effective functioning of the institutional system of the entity.

The increasing level of public needs as well as the difficulties arising regarding their coverage have required transformations both in the way of providing public goods and services, as well as in the way they are financed. At the same time, the quality of public services has become dependent, among others, on the performance level of territorial administrative units.

The territorial administrative units must respond with efficiency and competence to the concrete, daily problems that the citizens face, in whose service they must put their full concern. Thus, the development tendencies, in order to increase the performance, need to be directed, mainly, towards the integration and the assumption by the leaders of the political decisions taken, the definition and the setting of clear, simple and concrete objectives, the increase of the managerial responsibility, the monitoring of the activities and the obtaining programmed results, evaluation of results by designing and using an appropriate set of performance indicators.

The quality of the activities carried out is decisively influenced by the sufficiency of the material, financial, human or informational resources available to the territorial administrative units. The limitation of the financial resources, an aspect that most of the territorial administrative units face, affects the achievement of the objectives or makes it impossible to carry out activities attached to them.

The approach in the territorial administrative units is a vertical one, in which a person, who has the role of leader, based on the established competences, takes the necessary decisions for all the sectors of activity of the entity. Thus, the lower levels implement the decisions in the conditions in which they received them, and the obtained results are communicated the higher levels and used in the foundation of the future decisions.

The use of this pyramidal model of organization, based on rigidity, has negative consequences for the entity, considering that, an employee who

obtains excellent results and who has high knowledge and skills in the field, they are not used properly and effectively by the management. entity.

In our opinion, the flexibility in the process of corporate governance of the territorial administrative units and the use of personnel thinking and creativity in organizing and carrying out their own activities will lead to essential changes on several levels at the level of the public entity, namely the increase of the organizational performance, the improvement of the mentality and the behavior. staff in the way of exercising their tasks and responsibilities and orientation towards providing quality public services, in accordance with the needs and needs of citizens.

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